

Education Policies and Reforms from One Regime to Another and Its Impact on Education Equality

1. Introduction

Equality in education is fundamental to development of any country as it has been witnessed in countries like South Korea. In Kenya, the education system has evolved through different political regimes, each being an owner of policy agenda. From the era of President Daniel Arap Moi (1978-2002) through the presidency of President Mwai Kibaki (2003-2013) and the current President William Samoei Ruto (2022-Present) shifts in policy have attempted to improve access, relevance to labour market and quality, but the core question remains; have these changes improved education equality or have they reproduced new inequality in education hence income inequality? This essay seeks to argue that while access has broadened the frequent shifts in policy direction and the uneven capacity for implementation often work against the goal of education equality.

2. Education under President Moi

A defining change in education under President Moi was the introduction of 8-4-4 education system in 1985 which replaced the 7-4-2-3 System after the collapse of East African Community in 1977. This system involved 8 years of primary education, 4 years of secondary and minimum of 4 years in tertiary education. The 8-4-4 system was designed to emphasize practical and vocational subjects as well as academic ones. According to Sifuna (2011), an article on prevocational subjects in primary schools under the 8-4-4 system reveals that despite intention to introduce more vocational areas the lack of resources hampered realization of those objectives. In terms of access, the Moi era saw expansion of schooling opportunities, but many structural problems remained: teacher shortages, inadequate infrastructure especially in rural or marginalized regions and heavy emphasis on examinations. Rural areas, arid and semi-arid regions and children from less-privileged households often lagged behind their urban and wealthier peers. Despite President Moi's renowned 'love for education', education policy in Kenya was deeply intertwined with politics and patronage. Development projects especially ones that improves standards of living like establishment of schools often followed political loyalty rather than national planning that results in equitable economic growth and development. As a result, arid and marginalized areas like Turkana, Garissa and many others remain excluded in accessing education. The consequence of this uneven development is still visible today in these regions that were excluded from mainstream economic development since their illiteracy levels are high and hence limited economic opportunities.

In conclusion, while more children got into school in President Moi's era, equitability and quality were still the main concern.

3. Education under President Mwai Kibaki

One of the most remarkable achievements of President Mwai Kibaki's era was the reintroduction of a successful Free Primary Education Intervention in 2003. This policy significantly expanded access especially for children from socio-economically disadvantaged household and remote areas. This policy was first introduced in the early 1970s during President Jomo Kenyatta's era, the goal of this policy at the time was to fulfill the "education for all" after independence. According to Ojiambo (2009) this policy did not hold and quickly deteriorated as it was announced abruptly and the government did not give directive on how the 'lost revenue' could be recovered, as a result government could not fund enough teachers, classrooms, or materials, and school quality deteriorated. This policy collapsed because of several reasons and among them was lack of proper planning and sustainable financing. Lessons had been learnt by the time President Kibaki came into office and it worked better because of donor coordination and institutional accountability. This government secured significant external funding from development partners such as the World Bank before rolling out the policy. Funds were channeled directly to schools through the School Instructional Materials Bank Account (SMBA) and General-Purpose Account (GPA), improving transparency. These among other measures ensured that the policy was sustainable and feasible.

Another exemplary intervention by this regime was the introduction of Free Day Secondary Education in 2008. Although popularly branded as "free," the policy in reality was a tuition subsidy, as parents continued to shoulder costs for uniforms, meals, and other school-related expenses. Nevertheless, this initiative significantly improved access to secondary education, particularly for students from marginalized counties who had previously been locked out due to financial barriers.

3 Education under President Uhuru Kenyatta (2013-2022)

The education sector during President Uhuru Kenyatta's administration witnessed some of the most ambitious reform attempts since independence, particularly in the use of technology in learning and the structural reorganization of the curriculum. President Uhuru's education policies were grounded on the idea of modernization and preparing learners for a competitive global economy. The policies under this regime were visionary however, implementation challenges often undermined the intended outcomes.

3.1 The Digital Literacy Programme (Laptop Project)

Launched in 2013, the Digital Literacy Programme (DLP) popularly known as the "Laptop Project" was one of the Jubilee government's flagship promises. The initiative aimed to provide laptops or tablets to every Standard One pupil in public primary schools across Kenya. The

project's objectives were to integrate ICT into learning, bridge the digital divide and promote technological literacy from an early age.

However, the implementation faced major obstacles like procurement controversies, inadequate infrastructure (such as electricity and internet connectivity in rural schools) and insufficient teacher training delayed and diluted the program's impact. Instead of distributing laptops to each child, the policy was revised to provide a few digital devices per school, installed in computer labs. Although over 1 million devices were distributed nationwide by 2018, many schools lacked the resources to sustain or use them effectively. Studies by the Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) and the Ministry of Education revealed that most digital devices now lay idle due to poor maintenance and lack of technical support. According to Omboto et al. (2022), this intervention would have been successfully implemented and objectives met if teacher readiness and infrastructure such as electricity were taken into consideration first.

3.2. The Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC)

A transformative policy under Uhuru's presidency was the introduction of the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC), replacing the long-standing 8-4-4 system that had been in place since 1985. It started in 2017 in phases, and according to Muchira et al. (2023) CBC was designed to move away from knowledge delivery and exam-oriented approach towards a skills-based approach emphasizing critical thinking, problem-solving and preparation for labour market. CBC is 2-6-6-3 structure, aiming to produce all-round learners equipped with 21st-century competencies.

The CBC rollout represented a paradigm shift in Kenya's philosophy of education, as extensive research and policy consultations were done before roll out. According to Wanyama (2025), transition was rushed, teachers were not adequately prepared and many schools lacked the facilities to support the practical aspects of the new curriculum. Parents also complained of increased costs due to the need to purchase new learning materials and conduct project-based learning activities. Despite these challenges, early evaluations by KICD and UNICEF highlighted improvements in learner engagement, creativity, and inclusivity for learners with different abilities.

4. President William Samoei Ruto regime (2022- Present)

A notable education reform introduced by this regime is the 'New Higher Education Funding Model' by the Universities Fund to replace the Differentiated Unit Cost (DUC) system which previously public universities would receive funds per student programme. In the new model, students are categorized by their financial need and funding comes through a combination of scholarships, loans and household contributions. It utilizes Means Testing Instrument (MTI) to

assess the vulnerability of students and categorizes them as ‘vulnerable’, ‘extremely needy’, ‘needy, and ‘less needy’. It was started in 2023 with the students that sat for final secondary examination in 2022. This system has the potential to promote equity if implemented transparently and free from manipulation or technical errors. However, when the assessment tool mistakenly classifies a vulnerable learner as less needy, it can lead to irreversible exclusion from higher education, as the required household contribution becomes unaffordable. Numerous reports of such misclassifications have already emerged, prompting opposition from student bodies, university associations, and even triggering legal and constitutional challenges.

5. Conclusion

Kenya’s education landscape has evolved through successive political regimes, each introducing ambitious reforms that reflect political experimentation rather than a sustained national vision for educational equality. From the failed free primary education attempt, the successful reintroduction and expansion, curriculum reforms of President Uhuru Kenyatta, and now the tertiary funding and capitation in the current regime each phase demonstrates how education has often been a site of political experimentation. It is clear that many of these reforms were well-intentioned but their outcomes have been uneven, particularly for learners in marginalized and resource-deprived regions so educational expansion and reforms have failed to result to reduce income inequality because quality education in itself is still unequally accessed.

The pattern reveals that Kenya’s education system remains vulnerable to political dictates, where major reforms are introduced without sufficient technical preparation, long-term planning or alignment with existing capacities. Education being a fundamental right and a foundation for equality, should not shift with political tides. Each reform no matter how innovative should be grounded in technical consultations, comprehensive research, and evidence-based policy design that prioritize the learner’s welfare over political legacy.

For Kenya to achieve educational equality, reform must move beyond political symbolism to institutional continuity. This means creating evidence-based education policies that transcend regimes ones guided by inclusivity and accountability. This will ensure that every child has equal access to quality learning opportunities that prepare them to thrive in an equitable society, no matter who is in power.

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